

Role of MRI in Post Traumatic Stable Vertebral Fracture to Diagnose Spinal Injury – A Cross Sectional Study

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ABSTRACT

Vertebral fracture can be caused by direct or indirect trauma and are more likely to occur in patients with decreased bone density (osteoporosis, bony metastases). It aimed of studying characteristic imaging findings, to evaluate the role of MRI in patients with post traumatic stable vertebral fracture. All patients with history of post trauma were subjected to go for MRI examination. As MRI is the investigation of choice for soft tissue and spinal cord injuries. To ascertain the role of MRI in diagnosis of the spinal cord injury in cases of post traumatic stable vertebral fracture. It is a Hospital based Cross sectional study. A total of 119 Cases of spinal trauma who underwent MRI of the spine are included in the study. The Study was conducted in department of radiology over the duration of 18 months. All detailed history of patients was taken. The study has been done using 1.5 TESLA Siemens. Out of 119 cases, majority of the cases were >60 yr with male predominance. Blunt trauma [45 cases (37.8%)] was most common cause of injury among the cases and cervical spine [14 cases (28%)] was most common sites. MRI findings helped in detecting in spinal cord injury and soft tissue injury [50 cases (42%)]. Most common MRI findings were spinal canal Stenosis [73 cases (61.3%)], marrow edema [51 cases (42.9%)], spinal cord injury [50 cases (40.0%)], pre & paravertebral collection [14 cases (11.8%)], and IVD injury [5 cases (4.2%)]. Being a non-invasive procedure with high specificity and sensitivity, MRI is a preferred diagnostic tool to assess spinal cord injuries.

KEY WORDS: spinal injury, magnetic resonance imaging (MRI)

INTRODUCTION:

Vertebral fractures have a variety of etiologies including trauma, osteoporosis or neoplasm. An osteoporotic compression fracture has high prevalence among postmenopausal women and occurs less frequently in similar aged men^[1]. The young population is frequently involved in road accident, and incidence of fall from height. Spinal injury present in various severity & prognosis varying from asymptomatic condition to neurological deficit. Radiological imaging has important role in the management of spinal cord. MRI has been playing an important role in spinal injury due to specificity and sensitivity for detection of cord and soft tissue injury. MRI is first choice of investigation for evaluating the ligament and other soft tissue structures eg. Inter vertebral disc, spinal cord and occult osseous lesion.

Prompt and proper management of the patients with trauma from diagnosis to therapy can limit the neurological damage. A vertebral fracture is evidenced by vertebral body deformity or reduction in height of vertebral height beyond a certain threshold value in the absence of bone discontinuity. Vertebral fracture can be caused by direct or indirect trauma and are more likely to occur in patients with decreased bone density (osteoporosis, bony metastases). Fracture may be stable or unstable but there is a risk of damage to the spinal cord in case of stable fracture.

To Classify and describe vertebral fractures, vertebral morphology, reduction in height of vertebral body and location of fractures are consider. Osteoporotic fractures can be classified into three major types, depending on location of the fracture lines^[2].

Wedge fracture involving anterior (or less commonly posterior) edge of vertebral body. Concave or biconcave fractures, involving the central part of vertebra. Crush fracture, involving a combination of anterior, posterior and central elements. Types of the vertebral fractures:- vertebral compression fracture (m/c type); burst fracture; fracture – dislocation.

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https://www.pjsr.com/doi/10.24327/pjsr.2021.1407.01

Stability of the vertebral fractures: Stable – The structural stability of the spine remains intact. No neurologic deficits; Unstable – The structural stability of the spine is compromised. The spine can move as two or more independent units, which may cause spinal cord injury. Objective measurement of the vertebral deformity provides valuable information to the interpreting physician and helps grading fracture severity.

The goals of the diagnostic radiologist in spinal injury are to identify and correlate neurologic injury to vertebral fracture. There are some Imaging studies: Radiography - Plain radiographs are helpful in screening of fractures, but hairline fractures or non-displaced fractures may be difficult to detect; Computed tomography (CT) scanning - CT scans can readily detect bony fractures and help with the assessment of the extent of fractures; Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) - This is usually the investigation of choice for determining the extent of damage to the spinal cord. MRI is the most sensitive tool for detecting lesions of neural tissue and bone.

Within each group, the deformity can be graded semi quantitatively according to the loss of vertebral body height.

Grade 0: normal/unfractured vertebra ; Grade I: vertebral body height is >75% of normal value; Grade II: vertebral body height is between 50 and 75% of normal value; Grade III: vertebral body height is < 50% of normal value. Even more important is to assess the deformity of the spinal canal and neural foramina. In spine fractures, the spinal canal is often narrowed from translation and intrusion of vertebral body fragments of vertebral body height^[3].

MATERIALS & METHODS:

Ethics Proclamation: - All patients enrolled in this study were briefed about the nature and the course of study. Research Approval was obtained by Research Advisory Committee & Institutional Ethics Committee before the commencement of study.

Study Design/Study Type: - Hospital based Cross sectional study. Study Area & Source of Data: - The data for the study was collected from patients referred for MRI scan to the Department of Radiodiagnosis, People's College of Medical Sciences and Research Centre, Bhanpur, Bhopal (M.P.). Cases of spinal trauma who undergone MRI of the spine in the department were referred from various department of People's College of Medical sciences and Research Centre and People's Hospital, Bhanpur, Bhopal was included in the study. The study duration was

18 months from December 2018 to June 2020 and performed as per the standard protocol of MRI for spine.

Case Selection: The patients who were clinically suspected as a case of stable vertebral fracture were investigated with MRI. The study group had included a sample size of >100 patients selected by a purposive sampling. There are study variables:- Age; Gender, Site of injury; mode of injury; Risk factors; Radiologic findings; MRI findings; Disc involvement; Para spinal and soft tissue injury; Fractures; Spinal cord injury.

Inclusion criteria: Patient referred for MRI spine with stable vertebral fracture diagnosed by X-ray or CT scan; All the patients of acute spinal trauma undergoing MR Imaging form the study group.

Exclusion criteria: Patients who had poor GCS; with cardiac pace makers, cardiac defibrillators, ferromagnetic aneurysm clips; With cochlear implant, intra ocular metallic foreign body; Uncontrollable claustrophobia; Patients of spinal trauma undergoing MRI scan of spine after 2 weeks of injury and Diagnosed with unstable vertebral fracture.

Patient preparation procedure was briefly explained to the patient and consent was taken. Detailed history to rule out contraindication of MRI was specifically taken. Equipment study has been done using 1.5 TESLA Siemens Magnetom MRI. Standard surface coils and body coils were used for cervical, thoracic and lumbar spine for acquisition of images. Technique & Sequences, Patients were examined with MRI scan in the supine position with proper positioning and immobilization of the body, with quiet breathing and abdominal band compression. Standard surface coils were used for acquisition of images. Then images and report were collected & analyzed from MRI section of department.

MRI scanning was done using T1WI, T2WI, STIR sagittal, & GRE axial with slice thickness 4.5 mm x 5 mm. For spinal trauma contrast study was not done. Whenever required, thinner sections were obtained in the region of interest. A special MRI sequences like PD fat suppression and STIR were routinely obtained.

The MRI images were analyzed based on location (cervical, thoracic, lumbar & sacral), segment

of the spinal cord involvement, and severity of injury. In cases of trauma, site and level of injury, vertebral fracture, ligament injury, presence / absence of hematoma to classify into spinal subdural / extradural hematoma were noted. Follow up whenever possible patients were followed up and outcome recorded in cases of spinal trauma.

RESULTS:

This study is comprised on 119 patients who presented for an MRI scan of spine in the Department of Radio-diagnosis, People's College of Medical Sciences and Research Centre, People's University, Bhopal (M.P.) from December 2018 to May 2020 for the period of 18 months.

Those patients who fulfilled the inclusion criteria of stable vertebral fracture & associated with spinal injuries were enrolled in this study. Characterizations of the population and variables of recruited patient populations concerning different classifications are tabulated and graphically illustrate their distribution in different groups.

The present study designed as a cross-sectional observational study. Most of the variables used in our study are categorical in nature. Hence frequency and prevalence were calculated by Pearson's chi-square test also known as the Chi-square test for independence. A Chi-square test of association was also used to find if there was any relationship between two categorical variables.

The age of patients was between 10 to 87 years with a mean age of 46.4 years (Table 1). The majority were in the age group of >60 years (24.4%) followed by 31-40 years (28.8%), 51-60 Years (16.8%), 21-30 Years (12.6%), and <20 Years (10.1%).

The gender distributions among the patients

Table 1: Age Wise Distribution of Cases.

Age Groups	No. of Patients	%
<20 Years	12	10.1
21-30 Years	15	12.6
31-40 Years	26	21.8
41-50 Years	17	14.3
51-60 Years	20	16.8
>60 Years	29	24.4

were accordingly, Male (52.1%) and Female (47.9%) (Figure 1). Among the 119 patients in the study population group, the distribution of mode of injury is reported in (Table 2). Blunt trauma was found to be the most, majority with 45 (37.8%) cases. The other mode of injury were included in the descending order as fall from height 41 (34.5%), Road traffic accident 27 (22.7%), and Assault 6 (5.0%) respectively.

Figure 1: Distribution of Cases based on Gender.

Table 2: Distribution of Cases based on Mode of Injury.

Mode of injury	No. of Patients	%
Assault	6	5.0
Blunt Trauma	45	37.8
Fall From Height	41	34.5
Road Traffic Accident	27	22.7

All patients selected in the study had an X-ray and CT scan was 100% stable during the study. The study population was distributed based on spinal cord involvement which was diagnosed on MRI and it was present in 50 cases with 42.0% (Table 3).

The distributions of MRI findings among the study population were reported in graph 7. The vertebral fracture was accounted for in all cases 119 (100%) which was earlier diagnosed on either X-Ray or CT scan. The rest of the other findings were found as following in descending order of spinal canal stenosis 73 (61.3%), marrow edema 51 (42.9%), spinal cord injury 50 (42.0%), pre & para vertebral collection 14 (11.8%) and IVD injury 5 (4.2%) respectively (Figure 2).

Distribution of patients on the basis of involvement of spinal cord injury & level of injury

Table 3: Distribution of Cases on the Basis of Spinal Cord Involvement.

Spinal Cord Injury	No. of Patients	%
Absent	69	58.0
Present	50	42.0

was reported in (Table 4). Spinal injury with the involvement of the Cervical cord was maximum 14 (28.0%) of cases. Other levels including with spinal cord injury had following order Lumbar 11 (22.0%), Dorsal 10 (20.0%), Dorsal & Lumbar 7 (14.0%), Sacral 2 (4.0%), Cervical and Lumbar 2 (4.0%), Cervical, Dorsal & Lumbar 1 (2.0%) respectively.

DISCUSSION:

MR imaging is one of the most important tools in the diagnosis of spinal injury and helps to start a prompt and correct treatment for patients. Compared to X-ray & CT scan, MRI allows better visualization of various tissues, including spinal cord and ligaments, not to mention discs and vessels. This study was done with the aim to ascertain the role of MRI in the diagnosis of the spinal cord injury in cases of post traumatic stable vertebral fracture.

STUDY DESIGN & POPULATION:

The present study design is cross sectional observational study. Most of the variables used in our study are categorical in nature. Hence frequency and prevalence was calculated. Compilation of raw data & statistical treatment of data was performed using MS Excel & Medical 19.5 software.

Figure 2: Distribution of Cases on the Basis of MRI findings

Table 4: Comparison with other studies.

Studies	Mode of Injury							
	FFH	RTA	FOH	FOB	Physical Assault	Bullet injury	Bull Attack	
Hoque et al. ¹³	43%	18%	20%	-	-	-	-	
Islam MS et al. ¹⁴	50.5%	11.1%	15.2%	12.1%	-	-	-	
Razzak et al. ¹⁵	40.3%	14%	16%	9%	-	-	-	
Rahman et al. ⁴	45.4%	25.9%	17.8%	-	-	1.8%	-	
Rahman et al. ⁴	45.8%	24.7%	9.6%	9.0%	2%	0.7%	2%	
Moshiet al. ¹⁶	47.2%	62.8%	-	-	16.8	-	-	
Present study	34.5%	22.7%	37.8%	-	5.0%	-	-	

A total of 119 cases of spinal trauma who were undergone MRI of spine in the department of Radiodiagnosis referred from various department of People's College of Medical sciences and Research Centre and People's Hospital, Bhanpur, Bhopal were included in the study. The data were collected from December 2018 to May 2020 and performed as per the standard protocol of MRI for spine.

AGE & GENDER:

In our study, age of patients was between 10 to 87 years with a mean age of 46.4 years. The majority were in the age group of >60 years (24.4%) followed by 31-40 years (28.8%), 51-60 years (16.8%), 21-30 years (12.6%) and <20 years (10.1%). In the study by Rahman et. al, 56% of the patients were between 21 and 40 years of age and a study by Lenehan et al, reported 60% of the injuries in patients under 40 years of age. Nagvekar et al, reported 81% of the patients to be between 21-60 years of age^[4,5,6]. Similar results of other studies about mean age were reported as 47.44 years and 46.65 ± 16 years^[7,8] and not similar with Ulrich et al.'s study who found the mean age to be 36.1 years^[9].

As per Nalina et al,^[10] the commonly affected age group is 18–50 years and as per Flanders et al,^[11] the most commonly affected age group is 16-30 years. These observations by the above authors regarding the affected age group are close to our study.

The gender distributions among the patients were accordingly, male (52.1%) and female (47.9%). The most common gender affected was males in the present study. In a study by Rahman et al, the male to female ratio was 5:1, which was not found in accordance to this study. In a study by Nagvekar et al, 71% of the patients were males and a higher patient load of males was also seen in another study by Lenehan et al^[4,5,6].

Among the distribution of mode of injury, blunt trauma was found major portion in our study with 45 (37.8%) cases. The other mode of injury were had descending order as fall from height 41 (34.5%), road traffic accident 27 (22.7%) and assault 6 (5.0%). While comparing to a study done in Bangladesh was found quit concordant in which fall from height (45.8%) was the leading cause of spinal cord injury and road traffic accident whereas the second most common cause according to the study from 1995 to 2009^[12].

Various studies reported in literature were compared with our results and found similarity in mode of injury partially.

Spinal cord injury with involvement of Cervical spine was maximum 14 (28.0%) in cases. While at other level of involvement with spinal cord injury had following order: Lumbar 11 (22.0%), Dorsal 10 (20.0%), Dorsal & Lumbar 7 (14.0%), Sacral 2 (4.0%), Cervical and Lumbar 2 (4.0%), Cervical, Dorsal & Lumbar 1 (2.0%). In a study reported by Ning et al. they found that cervical region accounted for more than 54% of total cases, followed by thoracolumbar region for the level of injury of spinal cord injury. In another study cervical spine injuries 358 (40%) were the most common spine injuries, followed by lumbar, thoracic and sacral injuries^[13,14,15,16,17,18].

Comparing with other studies patients were distributed on the basis of spinal cord involvement and it was present in 50 cases with 42.0% involvement. While in a report it was observed as 43%^[19]. These observations by the above authors regarding the affecting spinal cord injury are close to our study. In another study level of injury among 57 patients, 43.86% had injury at cervical level followed by dorsal and lumbar levels 21.05% and finally, 14.04% had dorsolumbar injury^[20].

MRI is only imaging modality to assess spinal cord injury, to diagnose location and the severity of lesion and to detect extent of spinal cord compression and also helpful in detecting bone marrow edema.

Age & gender wise distribution of cases on the basis of mode of injury & spinal cord injury were also accounted. Maximum no. of cases was found for spinal cord injury in male was found for age group 31-40 Years 10 (32.3%) in road traffic accident and >60 years 8 (25.8%) in fall from height while in females maximum cases were observed in 50-60 yr age group 5 (26.3%) in fall from height. Such demonstrations were not found in any study and it was reported as total cases in male and female. In study of 57 patients underwent MRI for evaluation of spinal trauma with majority being males (86%) and young and middle aged men were the most common age group involved. Finally, it may be said no similar trend was observed in our study as reported in other studies with regards to MRI findings and with gender distribution^[20].

CONCLUSION:

Being a non-invasive procedure with high specificity and sensitivity, MRI is a preferred diagnostic tool to assess spinal column injuries & spinal cord injuries. We can identify gross osseous fractures, ligament disruption, soft tissue injuries with high precision and accuracy. However, it was difficult to identify the smaller posterior element fractures and incapacity of MRI in the case of patients with pacemakers and other implants. Despite its few disadvantages, MRI leads to provide prompt and accurate diagnosis, expeditious management, and avoidance of unnecessary procedures, thus, in the process of improving post-traumatic quality of life of patients of spinal trauma.

We conclude that spinal cord injuries are more common in males as compared to females and more common in the age group 21-60 years age group. Among all types of injuries like blunt trauma, fall from height is more common in males. The lumbar spine injury was found most common. The most common MRI findings in our study was Spinal Canal Stenosis followed by marrow edema and IVD injury was found in the least number. MR imaging is the only imaging modality to assess spinal cord injury, to diagnose the location and the severity of the lesion and to detect the cause of spinal cord compression. Moreover, the numbers of patients were limited in this study to accurately evaluate the effectivity of MRI in neurological prognosis.

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Cite this article as: Muzalda RS, Rai GS & Puranik S. Role of MRI in Post Traumatic Stable Vertebral Fracture to Diagnose Spinal Injury – A Cross Sectional Study. *PJSR.* 2021;14(1):1-7.
Source of Support : Nil, Conflict of Interest: None declared.